

Investigations on adsorption and leachability of methomyl on natural soils and risk of groundwater contamination

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Abstract : The behaviour of pesticides is strongly influenced by their interaction with soil as the latter is the ultimate reservoir for these chemicals irrespective of their application target. Adsorption and leachability are important processes which control their migration from soil to water bodies and consequently the extent of surface and groundwater contamination. The risk of leaching for methomyl in terms of Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) index has been evaluated based on its adsorption on five natural soils of different soil characteristics at two temperatures 20 °C and 30 °C by batch equilibrium technique and adsorption isotherms evaluated by using Freundlich's adsorption equation. To carry out adsorption study an extractive spectrophotometric methodology based on the transformation of insecticide into methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK) extractable yellow product absorbing at 380 nm has been developed. The GUS values obtained in the range 2.97–3.35 classify methomyl as leacher insecticide thereby posing a potential risk to both aquatic environment and human health calling for its judicious use.

Keywords : Methomyl, adsorption, leachability, spectrophotometry, GUS.

Introduction

No doubt the credits of pesticide include enhanced economic potential in terms of increased agricultural production, but at the same time their debits have played havoc with our environment. Pesticides become the source of soil pollution as soil is the ultimate dumping site for these species irrespective of their application target. Following application the pesticides enter soil and then move to aquatic environment through leaching. The pollution of soil and groundwater involves a risk to the environment and human health through residues in drinking water¹. In soil environment, the pesticides get fractioned between soil solution phase i.e. unadsorbed fraction (in free form) and soil solid phase through adsorption on clay and organic fraction (in bound form)². Toxicity of pesticide is dependent mainly on its concentration in soil solution phase from where it finds its way to water bodies resulting into the contamination of groundwater. Therefore, from environmental point of view, the study of adsorption phenomenon and evaluation of leachability of pesticides is of great importance to assess the ground

water contamination. The frequent detection of pesticides in surface and ground water has led to a number of experimental studies on pesticide adsorption by soils^{3–5} for the prediction of their movement in soils and aquifers.

Methomyl (*S*-methyl *N*-[methylcarbamoyloxy]thioacetimidate) an oxime carbamate is a broad spectrum insecticide which is widely used for the control of insects and nematode pests through direct contact and ingestion^{6–9}. It also acts as an ovicide against cotton bollworms and tobacco budworms⁸.

The WHO (World Health Organization), EPA (Environment Protection Agency) and ECC (European Chemical Classification) classify methomyl as a very toxic and hazardous pesticide⁶. The oral LD₅₀ of methomyl is 20.0 mg/kg b.wt. in male rats⁸. Toxic effects of methomyl includes inhibition of acetyl cholinesterase enzyme⁶, reproductive effects^{8,9}, genetic effects¹⁰, respiratory paraly-

sis¹¹, induce hematological and biochemical alterations in blood¹², decrease in total proteins and lipids¹². Due to the high water solubility of methomyl (57.9 g L⁻¹, at 25 °C)^{6,13}, it has the potential to contaminate the water resources. In view of the above, an extractive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of methomyl and subsequently validated to study adsorption on five natural soils of different characteristics consequently to evaluate its leachability and surface and ground water contamination. Of the various analytical methods viz. chromatographic¹⁴⁻¹⁶, fluorescence¹⁷, voltammetric¹⁸, amperometric¹⁹, bioassay²⁰, biosensor^{13,21}, the spectrophotometric methods^{7,22} being simple, sensitive, reliable find wide acceptance by laboratories of limited means. Further, the spectrophotometric procedure can also tolerate little interfering material and the equipment being cheap is easily accessible in all the laboratories.

The proposed method is based on the microwave assisted hydrolysis of methomyl into methyl amine which reacts with carbon disulphide and nickel(II) acetate in aqueous acetonitrile to form yellow nickel(II) methyl dithiocarbamate complex (1) which is extractable into methyl isobutyl ketone showing maximum absorbance at 380 nm. The most plausible course of reaction is :

That methyl amine is in fact formed from alkaline hydrolysis of methomyl and is quantitatively transformed into dithiocarbamates is well known²³⁻²⁵. The method has been successfully applied to the analysis of methomyl in commercial formulation and subsequently validated to study its adsorption on five soils of different characteristics for the purpose of evaluation of its leaching potential and surface and groundwater contamination. The various

adsorption parameters viz. soil adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}), thermodynamic parameters like Gibb's free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy change (ΔH°), and entropy change (ΔS°) for methomyl adsorption have been calculated. The effect of soil characteristics viz. clay and organic carbon content, pH, temperature and cation exchange capacity on adsorption of methomyl has also been studied. The leachability of methomyl vis-à-vis associated environmental potential risk has also been evaluated in terms of GUS model. Adsorption isotherms of methomyl were evaluated by using Freundlich's adsorption equation on five soils of different characteristics which is written as

$$X = K_f C_e^{n_f} \quad (1)$$

where X is the amount of pesticide adsorbed mg/kg of the adsorbent; C_e is the equilibrium solution concentration (mg L⁻¹); K_f and n_f are adsorption coefficients that characterize the adsorption capacity of adsorbent. The adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f are calculated from the least square methods applied to the linear form of the Freundlich's adsorption equation

$$\log X = \log K_f + n_f \log C_e \quad (2)$$

Another parameters for the adsorption process viz. distribution coefficient or soil-adsorption coefficient (K_d), soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}) and Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) have been calculated by using eqs. (3)-(5) respectively²⁶⁻²⁸.

$$K_d = X/C_e \quad (3)$$

$$K_{oc} = K_d \times (100/\%OC) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{GUS} = \log(t_{1/2}) [4 - \log(K_{oc})] \quad (5)$$

where R = gas constant, T = absolute temperature, $t_{1/2}$ = pesticide persistence (half life), OC = organic carbon content of soil. GUS score is used to study the leaching behaviour of pesticides and these can be classified as leacher in which GUS values are higher than 2.8, transition with GUS values between 1.8 and 2.8 and non-leacher pesticides with GUS values lower than 1.8²⁸.

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_d \quad (6)$$

$$\ln \{(K_d)_2/(K_d)_1\} = \Delta H^\circ/R \{(T_2 - T_1)/T_1 T_2\} \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = ((\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ)/T) \quad (8)$$

The thermodynamic parameters viz. Gibb's free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy change (ΔH°) and entropy change (ΔS°)

have also been calculated by using eqs. (6)–(8) respectively²⁹.

Results and discussion

The present spectrophotometric method is based on the color reaction of methylamine (hydrolytic product of methomyl) with carbon disulphide to form methyl dithiocarbamate which reacts with nickel(II) acetate in water to form yellow colored $[\text{Ni}(\text{DTC})_2]$ complex that absorbs at 380 nm. Effect of various experimental parameters on the development, stability and sensitivity of the color, vis-à-vis development of the proposed method has been studied before applying it to the analysis of methomyl in commercial formulation and soil adsorption study. The optimum time required for complete hydrolysis (in microwave) with maximum color intensity and stability (1.5 h) has been found to be 60 s with pH \sim 4.5 using universal buffer mixture (boric acid-phosphoric acid-sodium hydroxide)³⁰. Further extraction of coloured product into MIBK at this pH is complete and selective. Ni^{II} acetate and other hydrolytic product are not extractable into MIBK and hence do not interfere in the method. Under the optimized experimental conditions, the proposed spectrophotometric method obeys Beer's law in the range of 1.62–48.66 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for methomyl. The method is quite sensitive and the molar absorptivity (ϵ) and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $3.17 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.0511 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 380 nm. The method has subsequently been applied to the determination of methomyl in commercial formulation; the recoveries of the insecticide were in the range 93.5–96.2% of the nominal content with relative standard deviations (RSDs) in the range 0.6–1.2% (Table 1). The results have however been compared by an independent method²². The formulation analysis is

essential not only to ensure the quality of the marketed samples of the insecticide but also to get reliable residue/adsorption data. To assess the validity of the proposed method in soil adsorption study, effect of various common ions on the determination of the insecticide was studied. The method was found to be free from interferences due to common ions e.g. Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , OAc^- , PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , CO_3^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- ions present in soil.

The adsorption of methomyl is one of the major factors affecting its persistence and movement in soil which in turn influence the extent of surface and groundwater contamination. It is an important consideration for evaluation of the toxicity of this insecticide. Its toxicity is dependent mainly on its concentration in soil solution phase i.e. unadsorbed fraction of the insecticide which in turn is dependent on the soil characteristics such as organic carbon and clay content, temperature, pH and CEC of the soil type. In view of this, the proposed method has been applied to study adsorption of methomyl on five soils of different soil characteristics to evaluate its leachability which is an important process w.r.t. contamination risk to aquatic environment.

The adsorption isotherms of methomyl on five soils of different soil characteristics (Table 2) were drawn between the amount of methomyl adsorbed (mg kg^{-1}) on soils and that in equilibrium suspension (mg L^{-1}) at a fixed volume of water respectively. These isotherms have been classified as S-type of Gile's classification (Table 3) according to the initial slope of the curve (Figs. 1 and 2). S-type of isotherms represents a system where solid surface has high affinity for the solvent than for solutes (e.g. water competes strongly with solute for adsorption sites)³¹. Freundlich's adsorption coefficients K_f and n_f were cal-

Table 1. Assay of a commercial formulation of methomyl containing 40% active ingredient (Lannate)

Amount taken (μg)	Recovery (%) ^a	
	Present method	Comparison method ^b
4.05	94.2 \pm 0.7	91.3 \pm 0.8
8.11	93.5 \pm 0.6	90.5 \pm 1.4
16.22	94.8 \pm 0.9	92.6 \pm 1.2
32.44	95.3 \pm 1.2	93.2 \pm 1.4
40.55	96.2 \pm 1.4	93.6 \pm 1.4

^aValues are mean \pm standard deviation for 5 determinations.

^bReference method²².

Table 2. Characteristics of the different Indian soils used in the adsorption study of methomyl

Soil sample	pH	Clay (%)	Organic carbon (%)	Cation Exchange Capacity (meq/100 g)
I	7.2	32.6	0.8	13.1
II	7.6	18.2	0.9	12.9
III	6.5	20.0	1.5	11.0
IV	6.8	23.4	1.6	12.8
V	7.6	14.1	0.7	11.6

Table 3. Adsorption parameters for the adsorption of methomyl insecticide on five Indian soils at two different temperatures

Soil sample	K_f	n_f	20 °C			GUS	Adsorption isotherm
			K_d	K_{oc}			
I	2.53	1.21	0.78	97.88	2.97	S-type	
II	1.63	1.01	0.66	73.30	3.16	S-type	
III	3.06	1.32	0.93	62.12	3.27	S-type	
IV	2.02	1.19	0.95	59.63	3.29	S-type	
V	2.67	1.15	0.63	89.53	3.03	S-type	
			30 °C				
I	3.02	1.20	0.65	80.66	3.10	S-type	
II	2.21	1.07	0.57	63.54	3.25	S-type	
III	2.59	1.23	0.82	54.92	3.35	S-type	
IV	3.24	1.32	0.88	55.17	3.34	S-type	
V	2.37	1.10	0.59	84.80	3.07	S-type	

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherm of methomyl adsorption on Soils I-V at 20 °C (error bars represent the standard deviation of three replicates).

culated from the plot of $\log X$ versus $\log C_e$ from Freundlich's adsorption equation and the results are presented in Table 3. The adsorption coefficient K_f represents the amount of pesticide adsorbed at an equilibrium concentration of 1 mg L^{-1} and n_f represents the variation in adsorption with varying concentration of pesticide³². The observed values of n_f were more than 1, in all five soils types for methomyl, indicating that with an increase in the concentration of each insecticide, the percentage adsorption of each insecticide by the soil decreased. This might be due to the fact that at higher concentration there

may be difficult to access the adsorption sites.

The distribution coefficient, K_d is defined as the ratio of insecticide concentration in the soils and insecticide concentration in solution. The value of K_d considered as a prime approximation in characterizing adsorption capacity of methomyl in five soils³³. The values of K_d represents the extent of adsorption and in general higher the K_d value, greater is pesticide adsorption. It is observed that high K_d value in Soil IV and Soil III is due to significant amount of organic matter that exhibited higher adsorption capacity^{3,33}. However the high adsorption ca-

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherm of methomyl adsorption on Soils I-V at 30 °C (error bars represent the standard deviation of three replicates).

capacity of Soil I in comparison to Soil II was attributed to the high clay content. The clay particles with a wide surface area of facilitates adsorption which is essentially a surface phenomenon^{33,4}. K_d for a pesticide is soil-specific and vary with soil texture and its organic matter content, but the soil organic carbon partition coefficient (K_{oc}) is less soil specific⁵ and is calculated by normalizing adsorption coefficient (K_d) with the organic carbon (OC) content of the soil. The values of K_{oc} for methomyl on five soils types at 20 °C and 30 °C decreased as the temperature increased, indicating that adsorption is less favourable at high temperature³⁴. The CEC also influences the adsorption of pesticides. The value of CEC is directly proportional to hydrophobic nature of adsorbent i.e. greater the value of CEC of soil, the surface will be more hydrophobic (low water solubility) thus has higher adsorption affinity for soils with higher CEC and vice-versa³⁵.

Hence methomyl with high water solubility (57.9 g L⁻¹, at 25 °C) showed less adsorption for soils with large CEC values. The amount of pesticide adsorbed is also dependent on pH of the soil. In general, adsorption of pesticide is less in alkaline then in acidic soil³⁶. However, at quite high and low pH of the soil, the adsorption decreases due to change in clay mineralogy or destroying the crystal lattice³⁷. Similar behavior has been observed in the present study. From the forgone discussion on the adsorption of methomyl, the decreasing order of adsorp-

tion is

Soil IV > Soil III > Soil I > Soil II > Soil V

The thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of methomyl insecticide on five soils were also evaluated and are presented in Table 4. The methomyl adsorption decreased at higher temperature³⁸. This is due to the fact that the adsorbate-adsorbent bonds were weakened with increasing temperature. Generally, when the temperature increases, the pesticide becomes more soluble. As a consequence, it is less retained by the adsorbent^{3,39}.

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of methomyl on five Indian soils

Soil samples	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	20 °C	30 °C	25 °C	25 °C
I	-0.60	-1.10	-13.46	-0.0423
II	-1.01	-1.41	-10.82	-0.0322
III	-0.17	-0.49	-9.29	-0.0301
IV	-0.11	-0.31	-5.65	-0.0182
V	-1.14	-1.31	-4.84	-0.0121

The negative values of Gibb's free energy (ΔG°) for methomyl at two temperatures indicate the spontaneity of the adsorption process^{34,40}. The enthalpy change (ΔH°) calculated for methomyl were also negative, which indicates exothermic nature of the overall sorption process. The exothermic nature of the sorption processes show

that these processes are energetically stable, and that the sorption occurred through a bonding mechanism³⁴. The negative value of ΔS° shows an increase in the order of the system due to decreased randomness at the adsorbent and solution interface⁴⁰.

Groundwater Ubiquity Score (GUS) is the most commonly used model which relate pesticide persistence (half life) and adsorption in soil (K_{oc}). The leaching potential of insecticides in terms of GUS index was determined by using experimentally observed K_{oc} value for each soil sample and literature reported half life of methomyl⁴¹. GUS index was between 2.97–3.35 for methomyl (Table 3), which is higher than 2.8, which corresponds to a high-leacher compound. Therefore, methomyl may leach easily through soils with low OM⁴². This observation calls for the judicious use of this insecticide by adjusting the application dose according to soil type especially near the water bodies. Also the soils should be amended with farm-yard manure and compost which are rich in organic matter content in order to increase the insecticide retention and thus reducing its mobility. The latter application will also improve the soil fertility and health by serving as a source of soil nutrients.

Experimental

The spectrophotometric measurements have been made with Carry100 Bio UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Domestic microwave oven, Samsung was used to carry out hydrolysis. Genei (TM) shaking incubator, Bangalore was used in soil adsorption study.

Acetonitrile (Merck) was kept over phosphorus pentoxide (5 g L^{-1}) and distilled twice. The analytical standard of methomyl (Sigma-Aldrich) was used and its stock solution (10^{-3} M) was prepared in acetonitrile. The purity was checked by reported method²². Boric acid-phosphoric acid-acetic acid and sodium hydroxide buffer of pH ~ 4.5 was prepared by mixing equal volumes (23.3 mL) of boric acid (Ranbaxy, LR, 0.04 M solution in water), phosphoric acid (Ranbaxy, LR, 0.04 M solution in water) and acetic acid (Ranbaxy, LR, 0.04 M solution in water) followed by the addition of 30 mL of sodium hydroxide (Merck, LR, 0.2 M solution in water) to make the final volume to 100 mL³⁰. Potassium hydroxide (Merck, LR), acetic acid (Ranbaxy, LR) were prepared in distilled water. Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK, Merck,

AR) were used as supplied. Nickel(II) acetate (CDH, LR), its 0.01 M solution in distilled water was prepared. Carbon disulphide (AR, Merck) was used as received. The soils used in the adsorption study were collected from Solan District of Himachal Pradesh and were characterized at University of Horticulture and Forestry, Solan, Himachal Pradesh.

Preparation of calibration graph for pure compound :

The calibration curves were prepared on the best optimized conditions. Aliquots (0.1–3.0 mL) of standard solutions of methomyl ($10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ in acetonitrile) were taken in 10 mL measuring flasks and diluted to 3 mL with acetonitrile. Each solution was mixed with aqueous potassium hydroxide (1 mL, $\sim 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) and 3 mL of distilled water. Each solution was mixed with one drop of carbon disulphide ($\sim 100 \mu\text{L}$) and kept in microwave oven for 60 s. Each solution was then treated with acetic acid (2 mL, $\sim 0.1 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ in water) to neutralize the excess alkali and also to make the condition slightly acidic. The solution was poured into a 100 mL separating funnel containing 1 mL, 0.01 mol L⁻¹ nickel(II) acetate solution and 5 mL of buffer of pH ~ 4.5 (a mixture of boric acid-phosphoric acid-acetic acid and sodium hydroxide). The contents of the funnel were equilibrated two times with MIBK using 4 mL each time and total volume made to 10 mL with MIBK. The solution was dried by shaking with anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance of yellow coloured solution was measured at 380 nm against a reagent blank. The calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance values against concentration of pure compound. The insecticide determined in the linearity range 1.62 to 48.66 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with correlation coefficient of 0.99423.

Formulation analysis :

A granule (G) formulation Lannate, containing 40% active ingredient, procured from an authorized pesticide dealer was used. A single large sample of formulation equivalent to 8.10 mg active ingredient was dissolved in 10 mL acetonitrile and diluted to a known volume (50 mL) with the same solvent. Suitable aliquots of the above solution were taken and processed for analysis in the same manner as described above for pure compound. The assay results are given in Table 1.

Soil adsorption study :

Adsorption isotherms of methomyl on five Indian soils of different soil characteristics (Table 3) were obtained by the batch equilibration technique using 50 mL conical flask at two different temperatures i.e. 20 °C and 30 °C.

Triplicate soil samples (2 g) were equilibrated with methomyl solution in the concentration range from 8.11–48.6 µg mL⁻¹ on shaker at 150 rpm at respective temperature for 12 h equilibrium time (estimated time required for equilibrium to be reached between methomyl adsorbed and in solution). After equilibration, the suspensions were centrifuged and the equilibrium concentrations (C_e) were determined in supernatants by the spectrophotometric procedure described above. The various adsorption and thermodynamic parameters are given in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Conclusion

Pesticides are a major source of pollution of soil, ground and surface water and poses a serious risk to both environment and human health due to direct exposure or through residues in food and drinking water. The applied pesticide enters soil and then to aquatic environment through leaching and resulting into surface and ground water contamination. Leaching of pesticide is favoured due to its high concentration in soil solution phase (unadsorbed fraction of pesticide) which in turn is dependent on its adsorption in soil. The latter is influenced by soil characteristics viz. organic carbon content and clay, pH, temperature and CEC. The risk of leaching for methomyl has been evaluated based on its adsorption on five Indian soils of different soil characteristics at two temperatures viz. 20 °C and 30 °C by the proposed method. From its adsorption study it can be concluded that methomyl is adsorbed maximally in case of Soil IV followed by Soil III, Soil I, Soil IV and Soil V amongst the five soils studied.

The observed GUS values in the range 2.97–3.35 classifying it as a leacher pesticide in terms of leaching behaviour, thereby it poses potential risk to the aquatic environment. Hence, this insecticide should be used judiciously to prevent surface and groundwater contamination. The toxicity risk can also be reduced by adjusting the application dose according to soil properties and increasing the organic carbon content in the contaminated

soils. The latter will reduce the mobility of the insecticide.

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